

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

POLITICAL, LEGAL AND SOCIAL NATURE OF INTERNATIONAL NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS

Nishnianidze N.

Georgian Technical University, Professor

Qazumashvili R.

Georgian Technical University, Associate Professor

Abstract

The article deals with the political and legal aspects of the activities of non-governmental organizations and the peculiarities of their management. It studies and analyzes the role and significance of non-governmental organizations in a democratic society, as well as their influence on the current political and public agenda in the country, taking into account the peculiarities of domestic legislation and international law. According to the formulated hypothesis, the development of civil society institutions, non-governmental organizations, political parties, trade unions, associations, religious organizations is a necessary condition for the establishment of a democratic system, where the “key pillar” of formation, establishment and functioning of civil society are human rights, freedom, equality, establishment of political, legal and civil rights, which is examined in the context of the European legal system and the development of civil society.

Historical analysis, empirical, historical-comparative analysis and other research methods are used to study the problems posed in the article.

Keywords: Rights, non-governmental organization, political parties, trade union, association, religious organization, democratic, legal system, function, hypothesis.

Introduction

It is an undeniable fact that in order to improve democracy in the state, it is important to develop civil society in the right direction, which is reflected in the legitimacy of power, inviolability of human rights, protection of minority rights, distribution and balance of power.

At the present stage, namely in the late XX and early XXI century, an important role in the global governance of world politics is played by non-state actors, among which a special place is occupied by international non-governmental organizations that have legitimately secured their place as influential participants in international relations.

In Georgia and in the modern world, non-governmental organizations are an integral part of democracy, as a democratic state is unthinkable without the non-governmental - so-called third sector, which, in addition to being fully protected from state interference, is the core and constituent part of civil society, a guarantor of the high quality of democracy and, at the same time, a determining indicator of the quality of democracy.

An interesting trend is observed in relation to both international NGOs and local NGOs: the non-governmental sector is beginning to strengthen, including financially, in those areas where society believes that the fundamental rights of citizens, as well as democratic principles indispensable for the normal functioning of society, such as guarantees of privacy, freedom of property and speech, electoral rights, freedom of religion, etc., are being violated and/or restricted.

The main part of the essay

Civil society is “equipped” with important features, the activities of the society are not ad hoc, they unite on the basis of civic initiative to realize common interests, act independently of the government and take

care of the welfare of civil society in specialized areas to protect the interests of citizens and their rights. In addition, it is worth noting the mediatory nature of civil society organizations, which are “mediators” between the “non-civil” part of society and the government.

The development of international non-governmental organizations was conditioned by two main factors - the growth of political and public activities and the creation of various types of civil society organizations: political parties, charitable foundations, associations, educational societies and civic groups, religious organizations, analytical associations, media, trade unions, trade, public and professional associations. There are charitable, service-providing non-governmental organizations of various profiles, as well as foundations that finance non-governmental organizations and themselves represent a certain type of non-governmental organizations.

The phenomenon of non-governmental organizations has always attracted special attention. It is recognized that it is a multifaceted organism and dynamic phenomenon, the comprehensive, complex and in-depth study and research of which is conditioned by the needs of time, exchange of foreign experience, evolution of the legal system and public interests, which has further increased the importance and role of non-governmental organizations in civil society. Based on the above mentioned, from today's point of view, which concerns political-legal and social aspects of international non-governmental organizations in Georgia, this is an interesting, actual and in many ways important topic for the states in transition to democracy and post-Soviet countries, including Georgia, for effective functioning of the third sector and full use of its resources.

In Georgia, the place, role, goals and forms of implementation of international non-governmental organizations in the system of international legal relations,

opportunities to influence and impact on political processes as well as their active participation in socio-political processes taking place in the country are insufficiently studied; resources of the non-governmental sector are used insignificantly in solving international and local problems. Further prospects for the development of international non-governmental organizations have not been researched, although, given the Georgian reality and public opinion, there is a certain resistance to international non-governmental organizations.

In the article, we tried to present an analysis of the heterogeneous and contradictory attitudes formed in society towards the non-governmental sector. We believe that part of the international community fails to properly assess the purpose of non-governmental organizations, belittling their role and function, while non-governmental organizations represent a powerful ideological weapon in the domestic, state and international arenas. Within the framework of non-governmental organizations, many mechanisms have already been created and are operating in the field of international human rights protection.

For the full use of the resources of international non-governmental organizations in Georgia and the further development of the "third sector", we consider it necessary to solve the following specific tasks:

- Study of legal aspects of the activities of international non-governmental organizations;
- Review of Georgian government's tactics with regard to the NGO sector, taking into account the policy of international NGOs;
- Identification of the place and role of international non-governmental organizations in the system of international legal acts (multilateral treaties) and domestic normative acts, development of proposals to bring them in line with national legislation on the basis of comparative analysis;
- Analysis of the role of international non-governmental organizations in the system of international legal acts (multilateral agreements) and domestic normative acts, development of proposals to bring them in line with national legislation on the basis of comparative analysis;
- Analysis of the political aspects of the activities of international non-governmental organizations;
- Identifying the role and participation of international non-governmental organizations in the formation of international public opinion.

Of particular relevance is the fact that for the normal functioning of non-governmental organizations it is necessary to improve the legal framework, to form modern, legal, open social relations, to place non-governmental organizations in a unified legal field in order to ensure a certain order, which should cover four main spheres: legal, social, economic and political.

Legal regulation of non-governmental organizations determines the functioning of all four of these determinants. It is the interconnection of these topics and their holistic nature that requires proper research and analysis.

The first international non-governmental organizations in their modern form were established in the XIX century. The first such organizations were the British and International Anti-Slavery Society, founded in 1823¹. In 1850 there were only 5 organizations of this type in the world². As of 1905, there were 134 international non-governmental organizations, in 1958 there were about 1000, in 1972 there were 2190 to 2470 and in the 1980s there were more than 4000; gradually the number of international non-governmental organizations has increased significantly/ It should also be noted that the development trends of non-governmental international cooperation - "international cooperation" - was still at the dawn of humanity. At that time, "international cooperation" was very unstable and narrow - determining the venues of international trade fairs, meetings of scientists, etc., various types of international meetings - congresses and conferences - are considered the prehistory of international non-governmental organizations. According to reliable data³, the first congress was an international meeting of physicians in Rome, which lasted from March 10 to July 8, 1681 (three or four sessions were held each month).

For the first time, in 1863, an international non-governmental, humanitarian organization was founded in Geneva - the International Committee for Relief of Wounded in the event of War, which was an independent organization supporting the government in the humanitarian field. The Committee was later renamed the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC); on August 22, 1864, in Geneva, at the suggestion of the Swiss entrepreneur and public figure Henry Dunant, the Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded in Armies in the Field was signed. The Convention stipulated that doctors and medical personnel should have a universal distinguishing sign⁴. The red cross on a white background (an inversion of the colors of the Swiss flag) was chosen as such a symbol. The red cross became the first recognizable "brand" among international non-governmental organizations as a symbol of respect for one of the fundamental human rights - the right to life - and gave impetus to the development of humanitarian law as an independent legal direction⁵.

In Georgia, the Red Cross Society (GRCS) was founded in 1918, which was a voluntary, humanitarian, non-governmental organization. The society was considered an independent organization supporting the government in the field of humanitarian activities. The Georgian Red Cross Society existed independently from 1918 to 1923. After this period, the Georgian Red

¹ J. Huntzinger Introduction aux relations internationales / Huntzinger J. — P., 1988. — p. 209

² Union of International Associations // Year book of International Organizations: Guide to Global Civil Society Networks, 2000-2001. Vol. I. B. Munich, 2002. P. 2407;

³ J. Huntzinger Introduction aux relations internationales / Huntzinger J. — P., 1988. — p. 209

⁴ https://ka.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Red_Cross_and_Red_Crescent_Movement

⁵ Finnemore M. Rules of War and War of Rules: The International Red Cross and the Restraint of State Violence // Constructing World Culture/ ed. J. Boli, G. Thomas. Stanford, 1999. P. 149-168.;

Cross Society became part of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement of the Soviet Union. It functioned within it until the collapse of the Soviet Union.

Since 1991, the society has again been established as an independent organization. On October 16, 1997, the Parliament of Georgia adopted the Law "On the Georgian Red Cross Society", which defined the legal status, functions, goals and objectives of the Society. On November 20, 1997 the Georgian Red Cross Society became a member of the International Federation of National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies⁶. According to the article 14 of the No.415 Decree of August 26, 2008 of the President of Georgia "On Approval of the National Response Plan for Natural and Technogenic Emergencies", the Georgian Red Cross Society is responsible for organizing the activities of non-governmental organizations involved in the liquidation of the consequences of emergencies⁷.

The main catalyst for the creation of international non-governmental organizations was the year 1945, when the radically innovative Article 71 was included in the Charter of the United Nations, which gave non-governmental organizations the opportunity to legally participate in international relations and diplomacy. During the same period, the term "Non-Governmental Organization" entered the international legal vocabulary.

NGOs are created by public organizations or individuals from several states. However, they do not have international legal personality despite the consultative status "granted" within the United Nations system.

The concept of international non-governmental organizations is defined in Resolution 288 (X) of 27 February 1950 of the Economic and Social Council of the United Nations (ECOSOC). According to the Article 71 of the Charter of the United Nations, Economic and Social Council may make suitable arrangements for consultation with non-governmental organizations. ECOSOC considers international non-governmental organizations to be a link between the United Nations and civil society, with which it discusses policy issues as a partner⁸. According to the ECOSOC definition, any international organization not established on the basis of interstate treaty is an international non-governmental organization. Subsequently, ECOSOC clarified the criteria for the definition, according to which:

1. The organization must not be engaged in commercial activities;
2. It must be recognized by more than one State or have consultative status with any intergovernmental organization;
3. The source of funding must come from at least two countries.

As for the radically innovative Article 71 of the Charter of the United Nations, according to the UN Charter, the Economic and Social Council may make suitable arrangements for consultation with non-governmental organizations which are concerned with matters within its competence. Consultative status categories have been established - I, II and the "List": international non-governmental organizations of categories I and II may have their representatives attend open sessions of ECOSOC, the work of its committees and sessional bodies, as observers, while non-governmental organizations included in the "List" are authorized to have their representatives attend sessions only on issues within the competence of these organizations, where they may make oral or written statements.

However, there is a limitation - international non-governmental organizations do not participate in the activities of the UN General Assembly, the UN Security Council and the International Court of Justice. This activity does not have an international legal character and does not attribute to non-governmental organizations the status of a subject of international law. At the modern stage, non-governmental organizations play an important role in the field of both peace and human rights protection. In this regard, it is worth noting, for example, the activities of the organization "Amnesty International"⁹.

The concept of a non-governmental international organization is also defined by international human rights law (dictionary). In particular, this is an association created by several state public groups, unions or private individuals for the purpose of establishing and deepening international cooperation in political, economic, cultural, scientific or other fields. In order for an international non-governmental organization to have the appropriate status, it must meet certain criteria: it must operate in more than two states, and it must be international in nature in terms of its composition, goals, and financial support. Such status cannot be granted to branches of other organizations, educational institutions, closed clubs, etc. Many international non-governmental organizations have close contacts with intergovernmental international organizations. On the basis of an appropriate agreement, an international non-governmental organization is granted consultative status. For example, several hundred non-governmental organizations have observer representatives in the bodies of the UN system, whose rights are precisely defined¹⁰. Researchers associate a particular increase in the number of non-governmental organizations with countries that have an effective system of state governance and developed democratic institutions¹¹. Over the past decade, an increase in the number of international

⁶ <http://www.redcross.ge/about-us>, Who are we?

⁷ No.415 Decree of August 26, 2008 of the President of Georgia "On Approval of the National Response Plan for Natural and Technogenic Emergencies"

⁸ Muntyan M.A. Fundamentals of the Theory of International Relations, 2007

⁹ International Human Rights Law: Dictionary-Reference / [Authors: L.Aleksidze (ed.), L.Giorgadze, M.Kvachadze, etc.] - Tbilisi, 2005 - 283p.;

¹⁰ Heins V. Nongovernmental Organizations in International Society: Struggles over Recognition. New York, 2008. P. 43

¹¹ <http://cyberlinka.ru/article/n/npravitelstvennye-organizatsii-npo-kak-institut-razvitiya-i-pereustroystva-mira>, NONGOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS (NGOS) AS AN INSTITUTION FOR DEVELOPMENT AND PEACE

non-governmental organizations by hundreds has been observed around the world.

Non-governmental organizations are divided into three groups by the scale of their activities:

1. Universal, or international non-governmental organizations that operate in many countries around the world (e.g., Amnesty International);

2. Regional non-governmental organizations, whose members are individuals or legal entities. This type of organization operates in a specific geographical region. For example, the International Center Against Censorship, Article XIX is a non-governmental human rights organization headquartered in London;

3. National non-governmental organizations, whose activities are carried out in one country¹². In addition, there are non-governmental organizations of various directions (profiles) - charitable services, service providers, cultural, public, and others.

In Georgia and throughout the world, the non-governmental sector is an integral part of civil society, represented by a Non-Entrepreneurial Non-commercial Legal Entity (NNLE)) (NGO). The formation of modern civil society in Georgia began after the collapse of the Soviet Union and the restoration of independence. It can be said that since the 90s of the 20th century, one of the most relevant topics has been the development of civil society and the establishment of international non-governmental organizations in Georgia, because civil society could have a significant impact on a country on the path to democratization. Scientific, political, and business circles have actively begun to discuss how effective the civil sector was and what impact it had on socio-political processes.

It is undeniable that the meaning and purpose of civil society have been constantly changing over time, which is related to people's awareness and political activism, public involvement and the ability to exert influence. These processes are related to the discussion of the topic of globalization of civil society, which has been a subject of debate since the 1990s, as some theorists favor the establishment of the term "Transnational Civil Society", while others favor "Global Civil Society". In this regard, it should be noted that global civil society suffers from a certain theoretical and conceptual ambiguity, since global civil society is understood and discussed in two ways. In the first case, as a simple civil society - a peculiar form of social organization. In the second case, civil society is defined as a network of non-governmental organizations. In this sense, global civil society is considered as a set of international non-governmental organizations. Researcher J.Keane considers global civil society as a broader concept than simple non-governmental organizations.

Global civil society goes beyond the borders of the nation-state and operates on an international scale, uniting representatives of different countries in its network and organizations. Such associations direct their activities to the creation of international democratic coalitions. The main circle of the international community

are non-governmental organizations, which are transformed into international public organizations in a global format. An example of such a transformation is the influential human rights organization Amnesty International, the network of which unites about one million people - volunteers and donors in more than 140 countries of the world. However, initially it was a small British non-governmental organization, founded in 1961 by the English lawyer Peter Benenson in London. International non-governmental organizations include the international environmental NGO Greenpeace, the international human rights organization Human Rights Watch, Doctors Without Borders/Medecins sans frontiers, Reporters Without Borders, and Transparency International, etc. International non-governmental organizations themselves are united in coalitions, in the Union of International Associations, in the Alliance for Citizen Participation - CIVICUS. It is obvious that against the background of growing global processes in the world, international institutions and regional organizations create favorable conditions for increasing security, strengthening democratic values, and protecting human rights. Global civil society, based on the activities of international non-governmental organizations, is often considered part of the globalization process. Researcher J. Keane notes that global civil society, as a constantly developing social phenomenon, is an endless project. The goal of global society is to unite the world in a new way¹³.

Meanwhile, as in the rest of the world, Georgia has also seen an increase in the number of international non-governmental organizations and local non-governmental organizations. In the modern period, civil society organizations in Georgia mainly emerged in the early 1990s, when Western donors began funding organizations supporting the country's independent development. It can be said that since this period, civil society has become a pillar and a major instrument of public influence on political decisions. It was in the 1990s and later that there were founded the then-operating "Georgian Young Lawyers Association" (GYLA, founded in 1994), "International Society for Fair Elections and Democracy" (ISFED, founded in 1995), "Institute of Freedom" (founded in 1996), "Former Political Prisoners for Human Rights" (established in 1996), "Article 42 of the Constitution" (founded in 1997), "Kmara" ("Enough") (founded in 2001), "Kokoity Fandarast" (founded in 2007), "United States Agency for International Development - USAID, the United Nations Development Program - UNDP, Open Society Georgia (Soros Foundation), National Democratic Institute (NDI), Georgian Foundation for Strategy and International Studies (GFSIS), Swedish International Development Agency (Sida), non-governmental, non-profit research center CRRG Georgia and others, whose activities were aimed at promoting democratic processes, strengthening the civil sector and protecting human rights; the main source of funding for the NGO sector was grants received from international

¹² <http://cyberlinka.ru/article/n/nepravitelstvennye-organizatsii-npo-kak-institut-razvitiya-i-pereustroystva-mira>, NONGOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS (NGOS) AS AN INSTITUTION FOR DEVELOPMENT AND PEACE

¹³ Tsurtsumia M., Civil Society. Publishing House "Universal", Chapter V., Globalization of Civil Society., Tbilisi, 2011., pp. 99-108.

organizations / or foreign foundations, including Soros, Eurasia, Norwegian Refugee Council, etc., which is not surprising given the difficult situation in Georgia at that time - the extreme difficult social situation, a system of governance paralyzed by corruption, unresolved conflicts in Abkhazia and South Ossetia, civil war and much more.

During this period, all the efforts of civil society were directed towards regulating the political and economic space of the country and promoting the development of civil society. The country began to create legislation regulating the activities of the third sector and determined the rules for the registration and functioning of non-profit (non-commercial) legal entities. On June 28, 1996, the Parliament of Georgia adopted the Law "On Grants", which defines the general principles of granting, receiving and using grants in Georgia. On November 14, 1997, the Organic Law of Georgia "On Suspension and Prohibition of the Activities of Public Associations" was adopted, which determined the grounds and procedure for suspension and prohibition of the activities of non-entrepreneurial (non-commercial) legal entities, trade unions and other public associations in Georgia. On June 26, 1997, the Parliament of Georgia adopted the Civil Code of Georgia, which regulated civil-legal relations in the country and began their registration. The applicable Civil Code of Georgia determines the legal status of a non-entrepreneurial (non-commercial) legal entity, its legal capacity, the rules and conditions of foundation and issues of reorganization and liquidation. A non-entrepreneurial (non-commercial) legal entity is registered in the LEPL National Agency of Public Registry, operating under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Justice of Georgia, which includes state and tax registration.

In addition to the above-mentioned national legislation regulating NGOs in Georgia, the main legal framework is also formed by: the Constitution of Georgia, which enshrines the right to establish and join public associations; the Law of Georgia "On Entrepreneurs", which establishes the conditions for registration, reorganization and liquidation issues; the Law of Georgia "On Public Registry", establishing the terms and fees for registration of a non-entrepreneurial (non-commercial) legal entity; the Tax Code, defining the procedure, terms and conditions for obtaining and losing the status of a charitable organization by a non-profit (non-commercial) legal entity, the rights and obligations of the latter, types of activities, and a different tax system; the Law of Georgia "On State Support for Children and Youth Organizations" separately distinguishes children's and youth non-profit (non-commercial) organizations, provides a definition of the latter, and creates a register of such associations.

Conclusion

In the late 1980s and early 1990s, non-governmental organizations experienced significant development in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe, as well as in the post-Soviet space. The issue of defining the non-governmental sector as an integral part of civil society, its essence, role and forms was put on the agenda. Civil society was recognized as a necessary condition for strengthening democracy, since non-governmental organizations, being a key institution of civil society,

participate in monitoring and guiding the democratic development of the country, in the formation of public space, influence economic and social policy, ensure freedom of expression and association, and operate in the crucial areas of human rights, education, culture, social welfare, environment, employment, politics, science and humanitarian aid. However, due to these specific functions of NGOs, their activities are often perceived by the government as interference in state activities. The principle that underlies the unification of NGOs is noteworthy and worth emphasizing - their common interests, which are declared in the charter of a specific organization, while international NGOs formulate the realization of these interests in their own action programs, and their functioning is based on the principle of self-government, which is expressed in the fact that their activities are determined not by the laws adopted by the government, but by their own charter and program. They purposefully realize the set of goals of NGOs and the effectiveness of the means of their implementation. Civil society is a force to be reckoned with in the process of forming public opinion. The activities of most non-governmental organizations are related to the inviolability of human rights, protection of minority rights, and problematic issues of foreign policy. Accordingly, it is advisable to pay due attention to other no less important sectors, spheres, and directions, for example, the issues of high-mountainous regions, education, science, etc.

Establishing cooperation within the "third sector", that is, among non-governmental organizations, will contribute to the institutional strengthening of civil society organizations, the formation of common visions, and will significantly increase trust in non-governmental organizations in society.

References

1. J. Huntzinger Introduction aux relations internationales / Huntzinger J. — P., 1988. — p. 209;
2. Union of International Associations // Year book of International Organizations: Guide to Global Civil Society Networks, 2000-2001. Vol.1. B. Munich, 2002. P. 2407.;
3. Aleksidze L., Modern International Law. Chapter VI., International Conferences and Organizations. Publishing House "Lawyer's World", Tbilisi, 2015., 129-134 pp.;
4. https://ka.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Red_Cross_and_Red_Crescent_Movement;
5. Finnemore M. Rules of War and War Rules: The International Red Cross and the Restraint of State Violence// Constructing World Culture/ ed. J. Boli, G. Thomas. Stanford, 1999.P.149-168.;
6. <http://www.redcross.ge/about-us>, Who are we?
7. No. 415 Decree of August 26, 2008 of the President of Georgia "On Approval of the National Response Plan for Natural and Technogenic Emergencies"
8. Muntyan M.A. Fundamentals of the Theory of International Relations, 2007;
9. International Human Rights Law: Dictionary-Reference / [Authors: L. Aleksidze (ed.), L. Giorgadze, M. Kvachadze, etc.] - Tbilisi, 2005 - 283p.;

10. Heins V. Nongovernmental Organizations in International Society: Struggles over Recognition. New York, 2008. P. 43;
11. <http://cyberlninka.ru/article/n/nepravitelstvennye-organizatsii-npo-kak-institut-razvitiya-i-pereustroystva-mira>, NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS (NGOs) AS AN INSTITUTE FOR DEVELOPMENT AND REORGANIZATION OF THE WORLD;
12. <http://www.ctc.org.ge/news/discussion-process-report>, Public Attitudes towards Civil Society Organizations - Discussion Process Report;
13. Tsurtsunia M., Civil Society. Publishing House "Universal", Chapter V., Globalization of Civil Society., Tbilisi, 2011., 99-108 pp.
14. Burosi G., Rukhadze Z., Kvachadze M., Gaprindashvili L., Izoria L., Democracy and Citizenship. Part Four. Civil Society in Georgia: Past Experience and Future Challenges. Tbilisi, 2011.
15. „Polish Parliament Adopts New Law on Public Benefit Activities and Volunteerism”, Igor Golinski, International Journal of Civil Society Law, Volume I, Issue III, July 2003, pp.125.
16. „Guidebook to the Act of Law on Public Benefit and Volunteer Work”, issued by Public Benefit Works Council.
17. Social Economy and Law Journal, Winter 2003 – Spring 2004 Issue
18. <http://www.pozytek.gov.pl/What,is,FIO,581.html>, Official Web Site of Public Benefit Council.
19. Maria BAL, Kamila CZERWINSKA, Wojciech RUSTECKI: Volunteering and capacity building in Poland. What can Georgia take best out of it? p.7
20. Civil Code of Georgia (adopted on June 26, 1997);
21. <http://www.crrc.ge/1>, In the Caucasus, we are count(ed);
22. Civil Code of Georgia. Chapter Two, Legal Entity. Adopted on June 26, 1997, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/31702>;
23. Constitution of Georgia. Adopted on August 24, 1995, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/30346?publication=9>;
24. Organic Law of Georgia “On Suspension and Prohibition of the Activities of Public Associations”. Adopted on November 14, 1997. <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/29950>;
25. Tax Code of Georgia. Adopted on June 13, 1997. <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/31690>;
26. European Convention for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/40300>)
27. „European Cultural Convention“ <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/1211271>)